

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN APPROACHES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Makhmudova Dilobarkhan

English teacher of the 6th secondary school in Altinkol district, Andijan region

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Abstract. *In today's globalized world, the ability to communicate in foreign languages has become increasingly important. With the rise of international travel, business, and cultural exchanges, knowing a foreign language has many advantages. As a result, teaching methods have evolved to adapt to the needs of learners and to keep up with the latest developments in language education. This article will explore the significance of international experience and modern approaches in teaching foreign languages.*

Keywords: *CLT, strategy, ESL, instructors, TBLT, activities, discussions, Project-Based Learning.*

Introduction: Foreign language education has gone through large adjustments over the years, with educators always searching for extra tremendous and enticing strategies to assist college students in studying a new language.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT): CLT focuses on creating conversation capabilities through real-world, true interactions. It emphasizes the use of the goal language in significant contexts, encouraging college students to take part in conversations, role-plays, and problem-solving activities. This strategy prioritizes fluency over accuracy, promoting the notion that language is a device for conversation rather than a set of grammatical rules.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is a strategy that goals to reap communicative instead of linguistic competence via learner interaction. Born in the 1980s, this approach to language instructing is primarily based on the philosophy that, to research a language, one has to exercise the use of that language to talk that means to others.

Teachers who use the CLT strategy in English as a Second Language (ESL) school rooms inspire college students to use English. To promote significant language use, ESL instructors can make use of things that motivate college students to talk in the overall performance of significant tasks. Interaction is each the technique and the aim of ESL education.

In an ESL lecture room that makes use of the CLT method, college students do most of the talking. This allows college students to exercise speaking in English, consistently speaking with every other, instead of listening to an instructor's lecture. ESL instructors can inspire college students to engage with every different with minimal direct correction. The intent in the back of the communicative strategy to talking is to have college students exercise English except for concerns of awkwardness or making errors when mastering a new language.

Instead of interrupting or correcting college students when they make mistakes, instructors who make use of the CLT method may use oblique remarks or conversational redirections that no longer interrupt a conversation. They may reform inaccurate grammar (e.g., "his footwear is old" can be answered with, "yes, his footwear ARE old") to provide college students clues for additional conversation. However, variables such as age and skill ability can affect how advantageous oblique and direct remarks are in lecture rooms that make use of the CLT approach.

Real-Life Scenarios

Encouraging significant interactions, ESL instructors can make use of a vast range of individualized things to do and significant tasks. Students may interact in role-playing based totally on real-life situations such as discussing pursuits and famous culture, and negotiating expenditures when buying or describing the plot of an e-book or film they have lately enjoyed. The center of attention is on utilizing real-world conditions to permit college students to exercise the usage of language for context and content material rather than getting to know about grammatical policies and structure. Techniques encompass modeling, repetition, pair and crew work to assist college students in enhancing communicative advantage.

Working Together

CLT things to do are most positive when they enable college students to work collectively in pairs or groups. This mimics practical conversation that encourages fluency over grammatical competence. Research has discovered ESL college students commonly feel extra assured and relaxed practicing their language abilities and thoughts when working with different students. Since they are working with fellow English Language Learners (ELLs), they regularly experience safer speaking except for the worry of making mistakes.

Grouping and pairing college students additionally encourage engagement with in-class activities. For example, one may have college students work collectively to play a sport place they have to describe an object to every different in English so their friends can wager what that object is. Having college students work collectively no longer solely encourages them to interact with the language meaningfully, however, it additionally holds the conceivable to gamify the ESL study room and incentivize lively participation.

Fluent gives a beneficial listing of comparable "outspoken" things to do that incentivize significant verbal exchange between classmates, ranging from reverse charades video games to mock TV interviews.

Integrate Reading, Writing, and Speaking

However, research has observed that these pairing and grouping conversational methods are now not ample to promote lively participation in ESL classrooms. Instructors making use of the CLT strategy would possibly additionally encompass work reading, writing, and listening, as these competencies are additionally indispensable to Ells' improvement as an English language speaker.

The integrated-skills strategy to CLT brings these foremost language abilities together in activities. For instance, instructors may ask college students to watch a video online (listening), submit their opinion about it in the remark part (writing), and describe others' opinions from the remarks area (reading). Activities that combine more than one language competency can beautify communication-based ESL schooling by providing college students the threat to exercise a couple of competencies whilst additionally supplying instructors with a hazard to display quality practices in every one of these modes.

Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT): TBLT facilities around the completion of precise duties that require language use. This strategy presents college students with possibilities to interact in goal-oriented activities, such as planning a day trip or fixing a problem, which require them to use the goal language effectively. TBLT integrates language and content, fostering each conversation's abilities and cognitive development.

Technology-Enhanced Language Learning (TELL): With the development of technology, there has been a surge in the use of digital equipment for language learning. TELL comprises

several technological resources, such as language mastering apps, online platforms, and digital reality, to beautify language acquisition. This equipment supplies college students with interactive and immersive experiences, permitting for personalized and impartial language learning.

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL): CLIL combines language acquisition with the find-out-about-about of tutorial content. By educating topics like science, history, or artwork in an overseas language, college students advance each of their language and content material information simultaneously. This strategy encourages integral questioning and encourages college students to talk about complicated thoughts in a non-native language.

Flipped Classroom: The flipped lecture room mannequin reverses the standard mastering environment. Students reap publicity about new language substances backyard the lecture room through videos, online exercises, or readings. In-class time is then committed to interactive activities, discussions, and language practice. This strategy emphasizes student-centered studying and maximizes study room engagement.

Gamification: Gamification applies gaming factors and ideas in language getting to know contexts. It comprises aspects such as rewards, badges, and leaderboards to encourage and interact with students. Through interactive game-like activities, college students can exercise language competencies whilst having fun. Gamification promotes a dynamic and immersive knowledge of experience, contributing to elevated scholar motivation and retention.

Project-Based Learning (PBL): PBL entails college students working on long-term initiatives that require them to use the goal language to investigate, explore, and create. This method fosters collaboration, quintessential thinking, and problem-solving skills, as college students interact in real-world language tasks. PBL integrates language studying with significant and purposeful projects, making the studying ride greater proper and engaging.

Student-student interplay performs a fundamental position in making use of a communicative instructing approach. As the extra common instructing patterns have normally been as a substitute instructor dominant with college students commonly getting to know via passive listening, student-student interaction, on the contrary, focuses on the energetic interplay amongst the college students themselves for the duration of language training.

Student-student interplay embraces the techniques of cooperative getting to know in which every student's gaining knowledge of success is based on the total group's enter for the duration of the school room sessions. This is a high-quality way of attracting the total category as such workouts have interaction with all students, not simply the minority of lively college students who generally take part in a normal class.

One famous CLT recreation is role-playing. There is a playful element in role-playing that helps college students exercise talking except feeling the pressure. You can for instance assign components to your students, or let them determine a unique setting. Choose a theme that applies to students, or one that connects to different subjects defined in class. This will make certain that role-playing is a quintessential section of language training and not solely a stand-alone experience.

Collaborative duties like assigning scholar businesses to clear up a puzzle and the usage of solely the goal language are additionally famous things to do in CLT. This kind of workout permits no longer solely to decorate students' verbal exchange abilities and language competencies but additionally to scan with the peer-learning approach, which is beneficial in strengthening relationships amongst students.

There is nothing always well-known about these divisions in reality, although, to the native speaker of any one language, his very own classes are so acquainted that he finds them the solely logically viable ones and can hardly ever think about that different languages section truth in distinct ways. But a naive view of languages as all conveying essentially identical meanings overlooks quintessential variations and is vitiated via learners' errors; witness 'I am right here in view that 5 o'clock' (from a French speaker whose language has a one-of-a-kind cut-off factor between close to previous and present).

Not only do unique languages reduce the identical continuum in extraordinary ways, but, possibly even extra significant, special languages emphasize exceptional sorts of continua. Hopi, a North American Indian language, has a view of time that concentrates on the component of duration. Events of quick length which can be nouns in English, e.g. 'flash', 'wave', 'wind', have to be verbs in Hopi.

Hopi verb types categorical extraordinary members of the family in time, also. They do now not refer to the role of the occasions alongside a timeline as in English, however alternatively to their relation to the observer. This is not to say that both languages can't categorical the meanings of the other, however instead that there is a big difference between the meanings built-in, and the meanings that ought to be idea about and expressed.

In this sense, extraordinary languages predispose their audio system to 'think' differently, i.e. to direct their interest to extraordinary elements of the environment. The translation is consequently now not honestly a count number of searching for different phrases with comparable meaning, however of discovering excellent methods of pronouncing matters in some other language. Very often, the segments of truth that are structurally built-in into one language can also have to be disregarded in every other language. Thus, the twin number, although it can be expressed ('both', 'couple', etc.) has no area in the grammatical shape of English.

But there are many languages (e.g. Arabic) in which the shape of phrases (of the nouns, pronouns, or verbs) has to be splendid to singular, twin, or plural quantity, and audio systems are unable to keep away from watching the distinctions. Therefore, a speaker of English gaining knowledge of a language with twin wide variety of constructed will have to analyze it to pay interest on it. Different languages, then, may additionally categorize actuality differently or may additionally categorize comparable classes with the aid of distinctive linguistic forms.

However, the types are solely one component of the distinction between two language systems. The 2d foremost element pertains to the approaches in which language is used as a section of behavior in the several contexts of day-to-day life. To talk effectively, a speaker needs to be capable of categorical himself in the proper approaches on the proper occasions. It is now not ample to be in a position to use the linguistic varieties correctly. One should additionally be aware of how to use them appropriately.

Conclusion

International experience and modern approaches have significantly impacted the teaching of foreign languages. The exposure to different cultures, enhanced communication skills, and boosts in confidence and motivation are just some of the benefits derived from international experiences. Similarly, modern teaching approaches such as CLT, TBLT, and technology-enhanced learning provide effective tools for language educators to create dynamic and engaging lessons. By embracing these approaches, educators can cultivate learners' language proficiency, empowering them to thrive in an increasingly globalized world.

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